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Abstract

Participation in gambling online has to date been largely regarded under homogenising terms such as 'interactive gambling' or 'e-gambling'. This article explores different modes of participation gambling in the online environment, seeking to begin a process of better understanding some of the factors that construct distinguishable populations of online gamblers and distinct experiences of gambling online. The article commences with a brief overview of the internet, commenting on the apparent suitability of commercial gambling products for the development of successful online business models. Social and institutional factors constraining various modes of online participation in gambling are briefly outlined in relation to online wagering and gaming in Australia. Data drawn from three online surveys are then used to provide an overview of participation in the areas of online wagering and sports betting. These results form the basis of an initial analytical distinction between modes of participation in online betting on racing and sports in Australia.

Introduction

The development of the world wide web (www) as the popularly accessed aspect of the internet has intersected with the ongoing expansion of commercial gambling in recent years. This article describes aspects of emerging participation in online gambling from an Australian Research Council (ARC) funded study into the development and implementation of online gambling and sports betting (2000–03).¹

The article has four main parts. First, a brief background to the internet, as the primary medium for the staging of online gambling, is described. Secondly, the development of gambling as a viable form of e-commerce is outlined, followed by a summary of the legislative restrictions on participation in online gambling for Australia residents. The remainder of the article focuses on results from surveys conducted with clients of two totalisator operators (TABs), major Australian providers of online wagering and sports betting. Discussion and brief conclusions relate to emerging modes of participation in online gambling.

The Internet

The internet is, broadly speaking, a complex and diffused 'web' of interconnected computers, servers and switching points. The interconnectivity of the internet is recognised as being trans-jurisdictional in scope, ensuring that in many ways the Net escapes or overrides conventional regulation (Sassen, 2000). The image of the Net as a space of political and personal freedom which evades authority structures stems from its decentralised construction. In addition, the Net is considered a space of movement and change, where seemingly infinite processes of migration predominate over the instituting of permanent architectures or states. However, this imaginary of the unbounded and free space of culture neglects the extent to which the Net is, or can be, regulated and controlled.

The primary way in which digital space can be overseen is by technical means incorporated into the infrastructure that stages the Net and its organisation. One primary centralised authority oversees the granting of addresses and numbers and the domain name system. Although regulation is not a concern of this authority the presence of a 'gate-keeping system of sorts...raises the possibility of oversight capacities' (Sassen, 2000, p. 22). The Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN) was established in 1998 and is the central authority for assigning the numbers computers need to locate a particular address on the Net (Sassen, 2000, pp. 22–3). Technical controls and the principles embedded in technological innovations and solutions are also likely to determine in part whether the internet can be maintained as a predominantly public network or will become increasingly 'privatised' in the manner of telephone networks (McTaggart, 1999).

Possibilities for the governance of the space of digital culture also depend on whether the Net is viewed as one entity, which could potentially be governed by common policy and/or technical standards, or as an inter-networking of networks, which is too decentralised to be subject to external regulation. If the Net is envisaged as one system then issues of property and privacy become paramount. Approaches to defining and enforcing regimes of property and privacy rights in digital space could include handing some administrative functions and legal authority to global level bodies such as the World Intellectual Property

Organisation (WIPO) or a United Nations Framework Convention (Mathiason and Kuhlman, 1998).

It can be argued that the terrain of online digital culture, particularly in the form of the Net, is shaped by four primary factors. The first is the broad conceptualisation of what the Net could or should be. The dominant expression of what the Net should be has, to date, promoted an open space of virtually unlimited access. However, the likelihood of this remaining the case is uncertain. Secondly, the ongoing development of the Net's technical infrastructure is critical to how the internet does develop. Clearly, as the Microsoft antitrust case in the United States (United States Department of Justice, n.d.) indicates, there are technologically based strategies that may in some sense partially close aspects of the internet. The increasing significance of peer to peer (P2P)² on the internet is another example of how applications on the world wide web are likely to influence the future development and distribution of technology—exerting transformative influences on the terrains of online space.

Thirdly, the culture of the 'Netizens' of digital space should not be discounted. As increasingly digitally literate generations of young people continue to become involved in the construction and use of online space it is likely that innovators and innovations will exert substantial influence on the emerging online environment. Netizens are also likely to be represented across broad sections of society, so their influence can be exercised from a number of different points. This opens the way, particularly in the most technologically developed societies, to the type of synergies that can both implement and shape change. These three factors are, of course, all interrelated and the shape of the future Net will reflect all these influences.

The fourth factor and an increasingly important one is the burgeoning commercial space of the web, the tendency to close off large domains of the web (McTaggart, 1999) for the conduct of business to business (B2B) and business to consumer (B2C) activity. An increasing proportion of the world wide web is being utilised for the undertaking of commerce. Both business to business (B2B), particularly upstream purchasing, and business to consumer (B2C) activity have continued to grow in Australia (National Office of the Information Economy [NOIE] 2002).³ This article concerns itself with modes of participation of gamblers/consumers in gambling activity online, as such focussing on a form of B2C activity which implicates individuals located initially in the public space of the internet with commercialised or private domains (primarily `_.com.au` in this case).

The `.com.au` domain is the principal commercialised domain of the world wide web for Australian business and is likely to remain so unless the architecture of the internet fragments, possibly into multiple relatively closed private networks (McTaggart, 1999). As the 'dot.com' stock market crash suggested, the search for viable B2C business models, particularly in the realm of the mass selling of consumables, trailed initial enthusiasm for all things e-commerce.

However, there do appear to be certain products and services that are well suited to cybernetically contained modes of availability (demand) and delivery (supply). Perhaps the most suitable products are those that can be delivered wholly digitally. Most gambling products can be argued to fit into this model neatly. For example, all gaming products are wholly cybernetic, that is they take place within the central processing unit (CPU) of computers utilising random number generator (RNG) technology. Austrin and Curtis

(2001) posit that RNG technology will drive the 'normalisation' or rationalisation of gambling products into a 'single media' (2001, p. 36). This situation can only increase the significance of internet or online based products, surveillance and monitoring systems. Wagering and sports betting products are premised on a third event staged elsewhere; however, the bet can be offered and accepted online and RNG based gambling products which are nominally wagering products have already started to emerge.⁴

The possibility of the gambling industry developing a sustainable online business model that 'works' is thus largely premised on other factors, particularly consumer confidence in the medium, government restrictions on market access, the security and reliability of payment systems and privacy concerns. These are issues that are in the main not exceptional to the industry, but are part of wider issues surrounding the conduct of commercial activity in the online environment. These issues are, however, still directly related to traditional concerns about gambling and government regulation and the perception that the industry is kept relatively free of criminal influence and that the gambling products offered are fair. However, these questions and their interrelationships need to be re-evaluated from the perspective of individual gamblers in the digital age. In an online environment that is already transnational in its scope, gambling regulation and spatial location are not necessarily directly or effectively linked.

The Space of Legal Online Gambling for Australian Residents

The space of the world wide web and of digital commerce is, of course, also delimited by legislation enacted in national jurisdictions across the globe. These constitute attempts to limit the activities permitted in cyberspace and are therefore not necessarily defined entirely by spatial limits to national sovereignty. Indeed, in countries such as Australia and the United States the primary power to make laws in relation to gambling falls at the regional or state/territory level. In both these cases there is a lack of internal accord, between the thinking of national and regional level governments in relation to gambling, which pre-existed questions of transnational jurisdiction posed by the globality of the space of the world wide web. The situation is less complicated in the United Kingdom where a review of gambling regulation (British Gambling Review Body [BGRB], 2001) recommended a unitary national authority, the Gambling Commission, to take control of the administration of all gambling. Such unitary approaches are likely to be the longer-term model for other European Community (EC) member states, increasing the possibility of transnational agreements, for example on tax sharing related to online gambling.

In Australia, the Interactive Gambling Act 2001 (IGA) enacted under the Federal Government's telecommunications power is intended to proscribe the space of online gambling activity open to Australian residents. The IGA is unusual in the context of the regulation of Australian gambling, seeking as it does to impose uniform conditions on residents of all Australian states and territories, unlike the relatively piecemeal situation in relation to the regulation of 'terrestrial' gambling. The offences under the IGA relate to the provision (s.15)⁵ and advertising (s. 61)⁶ of 'interactive gambling services' to customers physically present in Australia. The definition of interactive gambling services is a broad one; however, subsequent exclusions to this definition effectively mean that the IGA prohibits the offering and advertising of online casino gaming, including table games and poker machines, whilst online wagering and sports betting is allowed.

The IGA, however, does not ensure national uniformity in relation to the space of legitimate online gambling. State and territory governments license totalisator operators (TABs) and bookmakers to offer race wagering and fixed odds sports betting online. In New South Wales, section 8 of the Unlawful Gambling Act 1998 is intended to prevent a person in New South Wales from betting on racing with off-shore wagering operators (Marzic, 1999). Further, subsection 30(3) of the Racing Administration Act 1998 is intended to extend a long-standing (and reputedly effective) prohibition on advertising into NSW by interstate bookmakers or totalisators to any 'electronic betting' operators not licensed in NSW (Marzic, 1999), or more specifically to the internet service providers (ISPs) who might host such online advertising. However, under the Racing Administration Regulation 1999 members of the Internet Industry Association (IIA) who are bound by the IIA Code of Practice are exempt from this advertising restriction (Marzic, 1999).

The practicability of enforcing the respective offences of the IGA and the NSW legislation is yet to be tested. In the case of the IGA, enforceability rests on a process that is complaints-driven. The Australian Broadcasting Authority (ABA) is responsible for receiving complaints that prohibited 'interactive gambling services' can be accessed in Australia (s. 20). Complaints, which can also be made about ISPs that are alleged to be in breach of codes or standards in hosting certain content, must identify the specific content, its webspace location and, where possible, the country in which the content is hosted (s. 21). The ABA has then to investigate what it considers to be *bona fide* complaints, and depending on whether the content is believed to be hosted in Australia or internationally, may refer the matter to the Australian Federal Police (AFP) or a foreign law enforcement agency.

There is also provision in the IGA (s. 15) for other jurisdictions to become designated under the Act, in which case proscribed 'interactive gambling services' that are 'Australian-based' may not to be offered or provided to customers in that country. The determination of whether an 'interactive gambling service' is Australian-based does not necessarily depend on the location of the gaming server but may be influenced by such factors as the location of the company head office (s. 15 A7).

The political dimension of the introduction of the IGA and the eventual form of its enactment should not be underestimated. Concern about the social impacts of gambling led to the Productivity Commission (PC)'s (1999) report *Australia's Gambling Industries*. The Commission identified significant levels of social harm particularly in relation to electronic gaming machines or 'pokies', promoting a general sense that 'something needs to be done' about gambling. Despite a Senate Select Committee on Information Technologies (SSCIT) review (2000) recommending strictly managed implementation of online gambling and an NOIE report (2001) which argued that banning internet gambling was not feasible, the draft federal legislation favoured an across-the-board ban. However, last minute political lobbying involving minor party Senators eventually led to the excising of the racing industry from the major restrictions under the Act and the redrafting of the IGA in its eventual final form. A Federal Government review of the IGA was called in February 2003 and is expected to focus on the potential under section 69A of the IGA to render unenforceable credit card transactions with illegal internet gambling services.

In summary then, the principal effect to date of the legislative process in relation to online gambling has been to set the offering and provision of internet gaming (casino table games and slots or poker machines) outside the space of legal online gambling for anyone

resident in Australia. Offences under the IGA do not target individual gamblers, whether resident in Australia or overseas, focussing instead on the providers and the advertisers of internet casino gambling.

The Surveys and Respondents

The overview of participation data presented here is drawn from three surveys conducted as part of the Australian Research Council funded research into the development of online gambling. The first survey (Survey A1) was conducted with account customers of one Australian TAB company. Customers were e-mailed a link to a secure website in September 2001. This ensured that only account holders were aware of the survey location. The secure website featured an introductory page featuring information about the project and the researchers, with a click-button at the bottom enabling access to the survey instrument.

The survey was available for completion for ten days and a total of 1,076 responses were submitted. Of these, 704 were complete records. The high drop-out rate experienced in this survey was due to the need to load ten successive pages to complete the entire survey. This survey was repeated in December 2002 (Survey A2), using the same delivery technique, but with a modified scroll down survey page that eliminated the need to load new pages.

A total of 1,775 responses were submitted, including 1,726 complete records. A number of questions were modified for inclusion in Survey A2 in response to feedback from respondents to Survey A1. The third survey (Survey B) was conducted differently, by recruiting respondents through the racing and sports betting websites of a second Australian TAB company. A small banner, linking to an introductory page to the survey, was placed on these websites in September 2002. This meant that both account holders visiting the websites and 'surfers' could potentially respond to the survey. This survey was also available for ten days and a total of 518 complete responses were received. Of these, 95.8% of those were account-holders with the TAB company providing the website.

A previous survey of internet gambling found a low participation rate (1%) amongst the population of internet users in the UK (Griffiths, 2002). However, this survey was conducted against a background of relatively low internet usage amongst the general population in that country (Griffiths, 2002, p. 5). This broad methodological approach contrasts with that utilised here, which focuses on specific populations of online gamblers and does not attempt to evaluate the participation rate of the general Australian population in online gambling.

The survey data is presented in such a way as to primarily enable direct comparison of the results of Survey A1 and Survey A2. These two surveys, conducted with the same closed sample population, can be read as directly comparable. The repeat survey enables confidence in the validity of responses and the observance of significant trends in the data. In many of the tables that follow, results from Survey A1 (2001) and Survey A2 (2002) are supplemented by results from Survey B. These results serve as a further point of comparison, but are presented in a distinct fashion (for example, see Table 1) to reinforce the different population that was surveyed in this instance. A variety of demographic information was gathered from respondents in all three surveys. A summary of the gender and age structure of the respondent population is shown in Table 1.

Gender participation reflects the traditional view that TAB betting is a maledominated activity (McMillen *et al.*, 1999). There is no comparative data available that would make it possible to assess whether the participation of women gamblers at TABs via the internet is relatively strong in comparison to other modes of access, such as telephone betting, visiting TAB agencies or outlets in hotels and clubs. This data on gendered participation is in contrast to that for online gaming participation, which showed that female participation at one well-established internet casino had increased from 45.4% of all gamblers as at March 2000, to 49.9% of all gamblers as at March 2001 (McMillen & Woolley, 2003). The population in Survey B is relatively younger and almost 6% more heavily biased toward males than the population in Survey A1. Figure 1 illustrates the population distribution of the three online survey samples. The Australian adult population (18 years and above) is also shown.

Table 1. Gender and age of survey respondents

	Survey A1 N = 704	Survey A2 N = 1,726	Survey B N = 518
<i>Gender</i>			
Female	15.3%	14.3%	9.6%
Male	84.7%	85.7%	90.4%
<i>Age</i>			
18–24	5.4%	4.3%	13.4%
25–34	17.4%	19.6%	27.8%
35–44	29.0%	29.0%	27.8%
45–54	29.2%	27.6%	21.4%
55–64	13.6%	16.4%	7.7%
65 +	3.8%	3.1%	1.8%

As Figure 1 shows, Survey A1 and Survey A2 have closely matched age distributions, with the youngest and oldest groups the most under-represented in comparison to the national age profile. Those in the age range 35–54 years are strongly over-represented in both these surveys. By comparison to surveys A1 and A2, the age distribution for Survey B is younger, with the age range 25–44 years comprising the most strongly over-represented group in relation to the national adult population.

The different age structure of the Survey B sample has possible implications for understanding different modes of participation in online gambling. Survey B may have captured a particular sector of the online gambling population, having been available only to those actively ‘surfing’ gambling-related internet content. This would tend to bias the sample towards participants in online gambling who utilised the internet for researching odds and bets available and compiling information. (There is a relatively high level of information and other content available on the gambling provider website which hosted the banner linking to Survey B.) Those gamblers who might normally utilise the internet primarily as a medium for placing bets and monitoring their gambling account would be less likely to access a survey that requires clicking through from a gambling provider

website. Such gamblers would be more likely to be relatively strongly represented in surveys delivered individually via email, such as occurred for surveys A1 and A2.

Figure 1. Comparison of survey respondents (age group)

Interestingly, people in the 55–64 years band are over-represented in surveys A1 and A2 in relation to the national population profile. However, those aged 65 and above are substantially under-represented in all three surveys. These data may reflect dimensions of the ‘digital divide’ as socially and technologically determined patterns of access and user capability in relation to the internet and information-communication technologies (Joseph, 2001). In 2000, 33% of Australian households were connected to the internet, a figure expected to rise to almost 50% in 2001 (ABS, 2002). Those who are most likely to be on the ‘wrong’ side of the digital divide include low-income earners, those lacking tertiary education qualifications, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples, those with disabilities, aged over 55 and women (NOIE, n.d.).

The contours of the respondent populations and the significance of the ‘digital divide’ in shaping participation in gambling online can be further understood by looking at data from surveys A1 and A2 in relation current work status, occupation and income levels. The figures for current work status are shown in Table 2.

Those who are currently working either full-time or part-time comprised the vast majority of the survey respondents. These figures compared to a national labour force participation rate of 64.7% and an unemployment rate of 6.1% in Australia in January 2003 (ABS, 2003).⁷ On this crude measure, the respondents to surveys A1 and A2 appear to have higher than average level of workforce participation and a low incidence of unemployment. In addition, respondents were heavily concentrated in three occupational categories,⁸ which comprised 70.1% of those respondents who were currently working (full- or part-time) in Survey A1 (see Table 3). In Survey A2 the same three occupational categories accounted for 69.4% of those currently working.

The two occupational categories that are most strongly represented in both survey populations, Managers and Administrators and Professionals, comprise more than half the total sample population in both Survey A1 (53.4%) and Survey A2 (55.8%). This

compares to the 2001 Census in which 18.2% of the working population were employed as Professionals and 9.2% as Managers and administrators, or 27.4% in total (ABS, 2002). From Survey A1 to Survey A2 the category of Managers and administrators grew as a proportion of the total sample by 4.4%, whilst the proportion of Professionals fell by 3.5%. The fastest growing category between surveys was that of Labourers and related workers.

Table 2. Respondents' current work status

Current work status	Survey A1	Survey A2
Working full-time	65.0%	70.9%
Working part-time	11.6%	9.5%
Retired	10.2%	9.0%
Other	4.4%	3.8%
Student	3.6%	2.8%
Home	2.6%	2.3%
Currently unemployed/looking for work	2.6%	1.7%
Total	100.0%	100.0%

All respondents were asked to nominate their income bracket. In Survey A1, 10.5% of respondents declined to answer this question, compared to 12.1% in Survey A2. The bias introduced into the results for this question by this higher than average refusal rate⁹ has not been calculated in the figures produced in Table 4, which are only for those respondents who answered the question.

Table 3. Occupational category of respondents currently working

Occupation	Survey A1	Survey A2
Advanced clerical and service workers	6.4%	5.7%
Associate professionals	3.7%	4.2%
Elementary clerical, sales and service workers	1.2%	1.4%
Intermediate clerical, sales and service workers	7.8%	7.0%
Intermediate production and transport workers	4.6%	3.8%
Labourers and related workers	5.8%	8.4%
Managers and administrators	26.7%	31.1%
Professionals	26.7%	24.7%
Tradespersons and related workers	17.1%	13.6%
Total	100.0%	99.9%

Note: Totals may not equal 100% due to rounding.

As a broad comparison, average ordinary time weekly pre-tax earnings for Australia as at February 2003 were \$860.50 (\$910.50 for males, \$772.10 for females) (ABS, 2003). Calculating this figure over a normal year arrives at an annualised figure of \$44,746. This figure is at a mid-point of the median income category for respondents to both Survey A1 and Survey A2. However, the average weekly normal time earnings for the predominant occupational categories comprising the survey sample, Managers and administrators (\$1,356 for males, \$1,146 for females) and Professionals (\$1,107 for males, \$921 for females), are the two highest paid occupation categories.

Table 4. Respondents' annual pre-tax income

Yearly income before tax	Survey A1	Survey A2
\$19,999 or less	16.8%	11.1%
\$20,000–\$29,999	12.4%	8.6%
\$30,000–\$39,999	16.0%	16.8%
\$40,000–\$49,999	18.4%	18.5%
\$50,000–\$59,999	14.9%	14.8%
\$60,000–\$69,999	7.6%	9.3%
\$70,000–\$79,999	–	5.3%
\$80,000–\$89,999	–	3.6%
\$90,000–\$99,999	8.1%	2.6%
\$100,000–\$124,999	3.2%	4.7%
\$125,000–\$149,999	0.8%	1.1%
\$150,000 or more	1.7%	3.5%
Total	99.9%	99.9%

Note: Totals may not equal 100% due to rounding.

In summary, the predominant demographic group amongst the respondents to surveys A1 and A2 appear to be males who are likely to be working full-time in professional and/or managerial roles and be earning above-average or high incomes. Such a respondent profile is consistent with the notion of a 'digital divide', with such employment and earnings characteristics likely within a sample defined initially by their participation in an activity predicated on skilled utilisation of the internet and information technology (NOIE, n.d.). A comparison of the results for Survey A1 and Survey A2 would also suggest there has been a mild strengthening of this demographic profile over time.

Participation in Online Gambling

This section reports selected results from the three surveys regarding participation in online gambling. As a guide, in Survey A1 almost half of the respondents (48.8%) said they had been gambling online for at least one year. In Survey A2, which was conducted 14 months later, 69.1% of respondents said they had been gambling online for at least one year. This compares to Survey B, in which 83.1% of respondents said they had been gambling online for at least one year. The forms of gambling participated in by respondents to the surveys are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5. Participation in online gambling activities, last 12 months

Gambling activity	Survey A1	Survey A2	Survey B
Wagered on racing online	92.7%	95.6%	94.6%
Placed sports bets online	34.8%	42.2%	85.6%
Gambled in an online lottery	7.7%	13.7%	24.9%
Gambled at an online casino	4.9%	6.9%	13.6%
Placed P2P bets through a betting exchange	n/a	4.5%	13.1%

Given the fact that all surveys were conducted through cooperation with totalisator operators, the high level of online participation in betting on races was expected. A trend towards increased participation in sports betting is suggested by the comparison between Survey A1 and A2. Also of interest are indications of increased participation in online lotteries and the emergence of betting exchanges. The prominence of online lotteries and

the emergence of betting exchanges in the 12 months leading up to Survey B and Survey A2 accounts for some of the apparent growth in participation that appears to be occurring. In relation to internet casino gaming, availability was already highly developed at the time of Survey A1. The small increase in participation levels suggested may, despite the efforts to restrict participation in internet gambling through the IGA, be due in part to growing confidence amongst gamblers in relation to the security and probity of off-shore gaming sites.

Table 6. Frequency of participation in betting on races online

Frequency	Survey A1	Survey A2	Survey B
Daily	7.0%	10.4%	22.3%
Weekly	46.8%	46.4%	50.6%
Every two weeks	11.8%	10.4%	6.0%
Monthly	13.2%	13.2%	7.6%
Less frequently	13.9%	16.8%	8.2%
Total	92.7%	97.2%	94.6%

The markedly higher figures for participation in sports betting, lotteries, internet casinos and betting exchanges recorded in Survey B can be partly accounted for by factors discussed in the previous section. The reliability of these results could only be assessed by a repeat survey using the same methodology. This caveat needs to be kept in mind in relation to further participation data from Survey B included below.

The high level of participation in betting on races reflected in each of the surveys is accompanied by a large proportion of high frequency or regular gamblers. If we define frequent online gamblers as those who bet on races online at least once every week then this group makes up 53.8%, 56.8% and 72.9% of the respondents to surveys A1, A2 and B respectively (see Table 6).

The increase in participation in race betting online between Survey A1 and Survey A2 includes a 3% increase in the proportion of gamblers who are betting daily. The increased levels of participation in sports betting online indicated in Table 5 do not appear to include a substantial rise in the frequency of this participation, as summarised in Table 7.

Only a small increase (0.4%) in the proportion of frequent participation in sports betting online is evident between Survey A1 and Survey A2. The majority of the growth in online sports betting between Survey A1 and Survey A2 appears to be amongst infrequent participants. There is a particularly marked difference in the proportion of regular participants in sports betting when Survey A1 (8.3%) and Survey A2 (8.7%) are compared with Survey B (45.5%).

Once again bearing in mind the difference between the different survey populations. It is likely that this can be largely accounted for by the different delivery method of Survey B, which required gamblers to be actively visiting the TAB website. As discussed earlier, this website is relatively rich in information and other content. Survey B appears to have located a sub-set of gamblers who, as well as being relatively broadly involved in online gambling, are relatively frequently involved in online race and sports betting.

Table 7. Frequency of participation in sports betting online

Frequency	Survey A1	Survey A2	Survey B
Daily	0.6%	1.4%	11.3%
Weekly	7.7%	7.3%	34.2%
Every two weeks	4.4%	3.7%	8.7%
Monthly	7.8%	8.0%	11.8%
Less frequently	14.4%	21.8%	15.6%
Total	34.9%	42.2%	85.6%

Alongside direct data gathered on participation in various forms of online gambling, the surveys asked other questions seeking to interrogate the breadth and intensity of individuals' involvement in online gambling activity. Selected results discussed here include those from questions asking about the number of gambling-related websites and other internet gambling resources utilised by gamblers on a regular basis, and about the number of gambling accounts held with online gambling providers. The overall numbers of websites used for gambling-related activity, including betting, gaming, tips, information and results, are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Online involvement in gambling, number of websites used regularly

Number of websites	Survey A1	Survey A2	Survey B
One	55.9%	53.4%	34.5%
2–5	38.2%	31.9%	52.5%
6–10	2.6%	2.4%	6.9%
11 or more	1.0%	1.3%	4.9%
Can't say	2.3%	11.1%	1.4%

A notable feature of Survey A1 and Survey A2 is the number of respondents who report utilising one (TAB) website for all their online gambling. This group of 'stay at home' gamblers comprised an absolute majority of the sample in both these surveys. Survey A2 featured a surprisingly large proportion of respondents who could not say how many gambling-related websites they regularly use. It would be unlikely that individuals who utilise only one website would be unable to answer this question definitively. Most of those who 'couldn't say' which category they fitted into are thus likely to utilise at least two gambling-related websites on a regular basis.

Survey B attracted a noticeably different distribution of responses to the same question. The group using between two and five websites here comprises an absolute majority of respondents. A much smaller proportion of respondents to this survey appear to be conducting all their online gambling activities via a single website. At the same time the proportion of respondents in Survey B who report using six or more gambling websites regularly was 11.8%, compared to 3.6% and 3.7% in surveys A1 and A2 respectively.

Once again, these data suggest that Survey B has captured a particular sub-group of online gamblers. This group may be considered a relatively active online group, comprising those who are prepared to 'shop around' for gambling opportunities or who may seek to

compile the gambling information they require from online sources. This suggestion is supported by data on the number of online gambling accounts held by respondents.

The results shown in Table 9 refer to the number of accounts held with providers of all types of online gambling, including wagering, sports betting and gaming. The results suggest that respondents do not have accounts at all gambling websites they utilise, which is to be expected given that a proportion of gambling-related sites are utilised purely for gathering information, tips or other resources. In all surveys those respondents who use only one online gambling account are in an absolute majority. At the same time, very small numbers of respondents utilise six or more gambling accounts. There are substantially fewer ‘stay at home’ gamblers present amongst the respondents to Survey B in comparison to surveys A1 and A2.

Table 9. Online involvement in gambling, number of accounts held

No. of accounts	Survey A1	Survey A2	Survey B
One	74.4%	71.9%	57.1%
2–5	24.8%	26.6%	38.0%
6–10	0.5%	0.8%	2.2%
11 or more	0.3%	0.8%	1.6%
Can’t say	–	–	1.2%

To further assess dimensions of involvement in online gambling, a participation profile of gamblers who use only one online gambling account was developed. It was hypothesised that the large proportion of gamblers who tend to ‘stay at home’ and utilise only one online gambling account, (a majority of the total sample in all the surveys), would participate less broadly and less frequently in forms of online gambling. Table 10 illustrates the forms of online gambling participated in by ‘stay at home’ gamblers. The shaded cells in Table 10 highlight results that deny the hypothesis that stay at home gamblers participate less broadly in forms of online gambling, that is these results show higher level of participation than for all gamblers (see Table 5).

The level of participation in online betting on racing for ‘stay at home’ gamblers, or those who use only one online gambling account, is marginally higher than for all gamblers surveyed. However, for all other forms of online gambling addressed in the surveys, participation rates for ‘stay at home’ gamblers were lower than for all gamblers. This supports the hypothesis that overall ‘stay at home’ gamblers would be less broadly involved in online gambling. Table 11 relates to the frequency of online participation in race and sports betting by ‘stay at home’ gamblers. The proportion of ‘stay at home’ gamblers who are frequent participants (daily or weekly) in online betting on racing is lower than for all gamblers in each of the surveys. In Survey A1, 52.0% of ‘stay at home’ gamblers were frequent participants in betting on races online compared to 53.8% of all gamblers. In Survey A2, 51.4% of ‘stay at home’ gamblers were frequent participants in betting on races online compared to 56.8% of all gamblers.

Table 10. ‘Stay at home’ gamblers participation in online gambling activities, last 12 months

Gambling activity	Survey A1	Survey A2	Survey B
Wagered on racing online	95.9%	96.7%	95.4%
Placed sports bets online	32.5%	38.1%	80.5%
Gambled in an online lottery	6.4%	12.3%	22.1%
Gambled at an online casino	4.3%	5.9%	10.1%
Placed P2P bets through a betting exchange	n/a	3.4%	7.4%

Table 11. ‘Stay at home’ gamblers frequency of online participation in betting on races and sports betting

Frequency	Survey A1		Survey A2		Survey B	
	Racing	Sports	Racing	Sports	Racing	Sports
Daily	4.8%	0.2%	6.5%	0.6%	19.3%	5.9%
Weekly	47.2%	5.9%	44.9%	5.2%	52.5%	34.4%
Every two weeks	12.8%	3.8%	11.4%	3.6%	6.1%	9.7%
Monthly	15.7%	7.4%	13.7%	6.9%	7.9%	9.7%
Less frequently	15.4%	15.2%	20.2%	21.8%	9.6%	20.8%
Total	95.9%	32.5%	96.7%	38.1%	95.4%	80.5%

Frequent participation in betting on races thus increased more quickly between surveys A1 and A2 amongst all gamblers (3.0%) than amongst ‘stay at home’ gamblers, whose level of frequent participation actually declined in that period (–0.6%). The level of frequent participation in betting on races online in Survey B was marginally lower for ‘stay at home’ gamblers (71.8%) as compared to all gamblers (72.9%).

The proportion of ‘stay at home’ gamblers who are frequent participants (daily or weekly) in online sports betting is lower than for all gamblers in each of the surveys. In Survey A1, 6.1% of ‘stay at home’ gamblers were frequent participants in sports betting online compared to 8.3% of all gamblers. In Survey A2, 5.8% of ‘stay at home’ gamblers were frequent participants in sports betting online compared to 8.7% of all gamblers. The level of frequent participation in sports betting thus increased more quickly between surveys A1 and A2 amongst all gamblers (0.4%) than for stay at home gamblers, whose level of frequent participation actually declined in that period (–0.3%). The level of frequent participation in sports betting online in Survey B was substantially lower for ‘stay at home’ gamblers (40.3%) as compared to all gamblers (45.5%).

The data across three surveys thus suggests that a majority group of online wagering and sports betting gamblers, here defined through the characteristic of utilising only one online gambling as ‘stay at home’ gamblers, participate less broadly and less frequently in online gambling activity than all gamblers surveyed taken as a whole. The correlative suggestion is that there are minority groups who utilise more than one gambling account online and participate more broadly and frequently than do the ‘stay at home’ gamblers. The data thus suggests that different modes of participation in online betting on races and

sports are emerging. We cannot provide full descriptions for these different modes at this early stage in researching this area, but some inferences can be drawn from the limited data that could be presented here. For example, it may be that for the 'stay at home' group, the internet operates predominantly as a medium for placing bets, rather than a knowledge-oriented tool for researching betting, compiling information and other activities organised around gambling.

For other respondents, gambling via the internet appears to involve a more extensive involvement in the online environment. In looking further at online activity organised around gambling, respondents to all surveys were asked whether they utilise non-website based internet resources in the course of their regular gambling activity. The resources referred to by the question were interactive or directly communicative in nature, including online messaging, chat rooms, e-mail groups, etc. In surveys A1, 3.5% of respondents reported utilising such resources regularly, with this figure rising to 4.9% in Survey A2. In Survey B the figure was 6%. These results indicate a small group of those participating in online gambling who are utilising internet based communicative tools, perhaps to share information or to socialise with other online gamblers. This suggests the possible emergence of what Wellman (2001) describes as 'personalised networking', in this case organised around online gambling activity. The sub-group of respondents who regularly used such communicative tools as part of their online gambling activity was too small to be considered totally reliable evidence of the development of such personalised networking 'communities' around gambling. However, the evidence to date suggests that a mode of participation in online gambling inclusive of networked social relations, developed in the interests of sharing information and knowledge of gambling opportunities, may be emerging and that further research should pay attention to this possibility.

Conclusions

The space for participation in online gambling by Australian residents is shaped and constrained by a variety of factors. These include legislative requirements, technological parameters and innovations, the interests of revenue-seeking actors (both private and public) in the commercial marketplace and specific socio-cultural practices emerging in the online context. This article has taken only a tentative first step in outlining some of the specific modes of participation in online gambling that appear to be taking shape in this relatively new space of activity. To this extent, the possibility of differentiating between a relatively circumscribed mode of 'stay at home' participation in online race and sports betting and more adventurous modes, featuring broader online involvements and the possibility of communicative social relations, was described.

The way individuals construct their own experiences of participation and senses of meaningfulness is crucial to developing a more complete understanding of the phenomenon of internet gambling. For example, the significance of gambling as gambling *per se* in cyberspace and of gambling as a particularly efficient form of online entertainment or leisure activity needs to be discerned. This will enable the further differentiating of modes of participation in online gambling, fostering greater understanding of the levels of financial resources and the extent of time and emotional commitments that various individuals invest in this emerging activity. The configuration of these aspects is also likely to be distinctive in the formation of mass and niche markets for online gambling.

The quite particular results discussed here thus need to be understood as they are contextualised within the processes of digitalisation that are transformative of contemporary social-historical and formations. According to Castells (2000, p. 11), 'we have entered a new technological paradigm, centred around microelectronics-based, information/communication technologies', which alter 'relationships of production/consumption, power and experience, ultimately leading to a transformation of culture'. The field of online gambling activity is one that involves new modes of participation in the digital universe and may be productive of new forms of cultural meaningfulness. The construction of 'cyberplaces' for gambling participation provides a clear example of the dialogic interrelationships between technology, markets, culture and forms of social practice in the 'network society' (Castells, 2000). As has been briefly outlined in this article, understanding the development and institutionalisation of modes of participation in online gambling will require all these factors to be taken into account.

The restricted focus of this article has meant that it cannot engage in a comprehensive way with many of the broader implications of the intersection between commercialised gambling and Castells' new 'technological paradigm' that are likely to emerge in the medium term. However, the study from which this article was developed has focused on many of these issues and some general comments about such implications can be offered here. The initial crucial point is that further development of the digital media that enable platforms such as the internet, wireless mobile devices (including phones) and interactive television is likely, over time, to expand the types of gambling products available and to enhance the likelihood of innovative forms of gambling being available wherever networking itself is available. Already, in the UK, a form of personalised and continuous interactive television (i-TV) bingo has reportedly attracted significant participation (Bulkley, 2003). This is indicative of the approach to online gambling being taken within the Department of Culture, Media and Society (DCMS) in implementing reforms following the Review of Gambling (2001) in that country. The DCMS appears likely to adopt a principle of *not* attempting to prohibit gambling via digital media platforms, but to license and control it through a new centralised regulatory authority (the Gambling Commission).

The UK government will thus seek to 'keep pace' with technological development and commercial innovation in relation to online gambling to a large extent, a fact which is unusual in the history of gambling where government policy and regulatory activity traditionally 'follows' as a response to developments in society (Austrin, 2001). Similarly, in Australia, state and territory regulators have sought to develop a national approach to the challenges of online gaming, the AUSModel (McMillen, 2001; McMillen and Woolley 2003). There is thus a strong likelihood that emerging forms of online or interactive gambling will be made relatively 'fully governable' (Woolley, 2000) in jurisdictions like Britain and Australia, that is, they will be made controllable, taxable and relatively free of criminal influence. To date the British approach, in particular, has appeared the least focused on restricting emerging forms of online gambling, perhaps motivated in part by the prevention of substantial taxation revenue loss to overseas locations such as Gibraltar (BGRB, 2001). This has likely flow-on benefits in terms of consumer choice for gamblers utilising British based gambling providers in particular, and of substantial taxation and other revenues flowing to the British government. The 'knock-on effect' of the various efforts to manage the liberalisation of online gambling, in terms of policy learning and implementation (McMillen, 1993), to other countries (and regional jurisdictions) with

highly developed networking capabilities and responsibility for the regulation of substantial commercial gambling markets is likely to be significant.

The scale of this commercial development, and its likely eventual emergence in other countries—under pressure from ‘home’ gambling companies in particular— has potentially significant repercussions for particular gambling markets. In particular, popular ‘terrestrial’ modes of participating in gambling may be affected. This is evidence of the continued reshaping of leisure opportunities by the intersection of digital media and commercial gambling. In Australia, for example, the currently predominant forms of this intersection, such as linked poker machine jackpots, have been facilitated by the integration of digital media and gambling into popular hotel and club leisure venues throughout Australia (Lynch and Woolley, forthcoming). The future ‘colonising’ of the home environment, the transformation of the household living room into, in effect, a node of a diffuse online (gambling) network, will further transform leisure preferences.

A rise in the popularity of various new and emergent modes of participation in online gambling may then have a substantial impact on existing gambling formats. The integration of live sports telecasts, commercial gambling products and i-TV capabilities, for example, is likely to underpin growth in recreational sports betting expenditures from the home, potentially impacting on forms of gambling staged in public venues.

Transformations in leisure options and preferences and in modes of participation in online gambling, also have implications in relation to the question of the ‘social harm’ arising from problematic forms of gambling consumption. The literature on problem gambling in Australia has largely, but not exclusively, associated social harm with poker machines (PC, 1999). The future proliferation of online gaming opportunities thus needs to be closely monitored and continuous research conducted in this light, (although this situation is made more difficult by the various national restrictions on gambling via the internet and the complexity of obtaining funding for, and conducting, independent transnational research projects). However, such research needs to be able to identify and assess transformations in the forms and patterns of social harm related to the specific ‘risk factors’ associated with online gambling (SSCIT, 2000, p. 52). In the research conducted for this project, for example, a small proportion of racing and sports betting gamblers reported problems related to their specifically *online* participation in gambling.¹⁰ The challenge to understand, and to adequately inform policy formulation in relation to forms of social harm that may emerge from participation in networked digital media-based forms of gambling, is made all the more important by the likelihood that such modes of participation are likely to constitute the new frontiers of commercialised gambling activity in the immediate and medium-term future.

Notes

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2. Without seeking to be definitive or to get into a technical discussion with many shades of grey, peer to peer (P2P) applications can be understood as transforming to some extent the role of the PCs connected to the edge of the internet. Instead of being clients of a server with a fixed domain name server (DNS) address, PCs use P2P applications (and not all of these applications operate in the same way) to become the nodes of the system (peers) themselves, operating and coping with the dynamic connectivity environment largely or entirely outside the DNS system.
3. According to the April 2002 *State of Play* report produced periodically by the National Office for the Information Economy (NOIE), 50% of Australians over the age of 16 years who browse the internet also make purchases online. This compares to figures between 65–7% on this measure for countries such as the USA, Germany and Sweden, and is closely matched to figures for countries such as New Zealand, France and South Korea.
4. For example, 'quick pick' type 'bets' on horse racing are a form of random, lottery-style draw.
5. Maximum penalty under this provision is \$220,000 per day for individuals and \$1.1 million for corporations.
6. Maximum penalty \$13,200 per day for individuals and \$66,000 per day for corporations.
7. This participation rate includes anyone over the age of 15 years who has done one hour of paid work or more in the reference week, with the exception of those on leave, etc. (see ABS Cat. 6202.0).
8. As officially categorised by the Australian Bureau of Statistics, Cat. 1221.0.
9. For example, other demography questions such as age, gender, education, work status, etc. had refusal rates in the range 1–2%.
10. This and other areas of the project research will be a focus of forthcoming publications.

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